

DIGITAL PRODUCT PASSPORT READINESS

*PRELIMINARY EVIDENCE ON REGULATORY INFORMATION GAPS,
DIGITALISATION CHALLENGES, AND SERVICE PROVIDER ENGAGEMENT*

10/04/2026

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Abstract	This report presents preliminary findings from surveys and interviews conducted between December 2025 and March 2026 within the CIRPASS-2 EWG1 and CoP, covering the availability of regulatory information, organisational digitalisation challenges, and practical considerations for working with DPPSPs. Respondents broadly agree that publicly available regulatory information is insufficient and inaccessible, and that DPP readiness faces more challenges than an information gap alone. DPPSPs are found to bear a significant educational burden. The analysis is descriptive in nature; broader conclusions and recommendations will be developed as more data and feedback is collected.
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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DPP	Digital Product Passport
DPPaaS	Digital Product Passport as a Service
DPPSP	Digital Product Passport Service Providers
CoP	Community of Practice
EC	European Commission
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
ESPR	Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation
EU	European Union
EWG	Expert Working Groups
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
PIM	Product Information Management
PLM	Product Lifecycle Management
rEO	Responsible Economic Operator
SME	Small-Medium Enterprise

1 INTRODUCTION

The Digital Product Passport (DPP), established under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), is considered one of the European Union's key regulatory instruments for advancing both digitalisation and circular economy objectives. The DPP aims to provide a digital record of product-related information across the product lifecycle, enabling access to data for a wide range of stakeholders, from regulators and market surveillance authorities to businesses and consumers. By facilitating the exchange of product information, the DPP is expected to support regulatory compliance, supply-chain transparency, and improved downstream product management.

The development of the DPP framework has generated significant interest across industries and the digital services ecosystem. A new market segment of DPP service providers (DPPSP) has rapidly emerged to support companies in implementing DPP systems and managing product information. This growing ecosystem is reflected by a number of figures. Nearly 500 organisations have self-identified as DPPSPs within the CIRPASS-2 Community of Practice (CoP) alone. The projected global market sizes are USD 1,780.5 million by 2030¹ and USD 2,996.1 million by 2033².

While this momentum reflects both policy ambition and business opportunity, it also highlights the practical challenges companies face. The initial hurdle for all is staying informed about evolving DPP-related regulatory developments, both cross-sectoral and sector specific, and broader product information requirements. DPP implementation also often require companies to assess and strengthen their internal digital capabilities to make sure they will fulfil DPP requirements and leverage available DPP data. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are likely to face these two challenges most acutely, and new challenges related to entering into a partnership with a DPPSP.

To explore these three related topics: **(1) challenges in staying informed about DPP-related regulations, (2) organisational digitalisation challenges relevant to DPP implementation, and (3) practical considerations in working with DPPSPs**, several surveys and in-depth interviews were conducted between December 2025 and March 2026 within CIRPASS-2 stakeholder network.

The remainder of this report is structured as follow:

- Section 2 describes the methodology underpinning the data collection activities
- Section 3 presents findings from the WG1 survey on regulatory information availability and digitalisation readiness
- Section 4 presents findings from the CoP survey on working effectively with DPPSPs
- Section 5 offers conclusions

¹ <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/digital-product-passport-market-163607839.html>

² <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/digital-product-passport-market-report>

2 METHODOLOGY

This report describes analysis findings from the surveys and interviewed mentioned above. The surveys were designed to address distinct questions, reflecting the roles and perspectives of the two respondent groups. As such, the surveys are treated separately throughout the report and are not aggregated.

Members of the CIRPASS-2 Expert Working Group 1 (EWG1), formally known as *Observatory Board: European and Global Regulatory Context*, were surveyed on the availability and quality of publicly available DPP regulatory information. EWG1 was selected given its mandate to monitor DPP-related policies and regulations, both European and beyond, as well as other regulatory developments affecting DPP implementation and assessment (e.g. circularity measurements, sustainability, material safety, substances of concern). The survey also aimed to identify digital support instruments that could support SMEs, particularly in data collection and structuring, a well-identified problem across sectors.

In parallel, in-depth interviews were conducted with several industry associations to better understand their role in supporting member companies, particularly SME, in staying informed and preparing for DPP implementation. These interviews revealed the important role played by DPPSPs: in many cases, service providers were described as the first point of contact through which companies become aware of DPP and begin to form their understanding of its implications.

This observation aligns with a recurring question raised by companies: how to identify and effectively work with a DPPSP. To explore this further, an additional survey was conducted within the CIRPASS-2 Community of Practice (CoP), inviting DPPSPs to share their perspectives on how companies (i.e. their future clients), including SMEs, should engage with them effectively.

These insights are particularly timely given the ongoing development of delegated acts under the ESPR concerning DPP. As the regulatory framework and implementation requirements continue to evolve, a clearer understanding of how companies access regulatory information, develop digital capabilities, and interact with DPP service providers can offer useful evidence for stakeholders involved in designing and operationalizing the DPP ecosystem.

All survey responses were collected anonymously, and no personally identifiable information was used in the analysis. The findings presented in this report are based exclusively on aggregate analysis of responses across the full respondent pool. Where breakdowns by organisational type are discussed, these are presented at the category level only, and no attempt is made to attribute specific responses to individual organisations or respondents.

3 EXPERT WORKING GROUP 1 (EWG1) SURVEY

EWG1 survey was conducted in December 2025. The purpose of the survey was to clarify the challenges of keeping up with regulatory development and availability of digitalization support policies of SMEs. **Figure 1** illustrates the composition of survey respondents by organisational category, as a proportion of total responses.

Respondents represented a diverse range of organisational types, with a total of 27 responses received. The largest group was DPPSP (11 respondents), followed by large organisation manufacturers (4), associations (3), standardization bodies (2), SME consultants (2), and universities (2). Single responses were received from an SME manufacturer, a large organisation consultant, and a SaaS platform focused on digitizing supply chains.

The relatively high proportion of DPP service provider respondents warrants a brief note. This does not necessarily introduce bias into the findings; rather, given that service providers have a strong incentive to engage with as wide a range of companies as possible, they may in fact be well-positioned to offer a grounded view of the challenges companies, and SMEs in particular, face in navigating DPP requirements. That said, drawing firm conclusions about the representativeness of the sample would be premature at this stage.

FIGURE 1: RESPONDENT DISTRIBUTION BY ORGANISATION TYPE

3.1 REGULATORY INFORMATION AVAILABILITY AND QUALITY

3.1.1 REGULATORY INFORMATION AVAILABILITY

A strong majority (70%) of respondents indicated that affordable resources, whether public or private, are insufficient for SMEs to familiarize themselves with EU product regulations such as EPR (Figure 2).

This was the result of the question "Do you think there are enough available affordable resources available for SMEs publicly or privately to familiarize themselves with EU product regulations, such as the EPR (EU/2024/1781)". The breakdown by organisational type reinforces this picture (Figure 3). All three associations and all five large organisation respondents (four manufacturers and one consultant) answered "No" without exception, indicating a consistent view. DPPSPs followed a similar pattern: seven answered "No" and three were "Not sure," suggesting that even those who operate closest to DPP implementation and stand to benefit from greater market awareness broadly share the assessment that resources remain insufficient. The explanations to this sentiment, which is analysed in the next section, strongly reinforce this. Even "Yes" responses come with important caveats.

FIGURE 2: AFFORDABLE INFORMATION RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

FIGURE 3: INFORMATION RESOURCE AVAILABILITY BY ORGANISATION TYPES

FIGURE 4: EXPLANATIONS OF SENTIMENTS ON INFORMATION AVAILABILITY

The respondents were also asked to provide reasons. In a word cloud (Figure 4) of responses, terms that appear more frequently across responses are rendered in larger text, providing a visual indication of the themes most commonly raised by respondents. Text analysis then identified several key themes across the explanations.

- *Regulatory information exists but is fragmented and hard to find.* This is the single most recurring theme. Respondents consistently describe regulation information as "scattered," "spread across different platforms," "not easily accessible," and requiring significant effort to piece together. The EU website itself is described as "hard to read." This came up in roughly in a third of all responses.
- *Complexity is a barrier, not just availability.* Several respondents indicate that even when information exists, it is written for experts and is far too complex for SMEs to act on. Phrases like "too complex and too bureaucratic," "only understandable to experts," and "cuts across various cross-business functions" point to a usability gap beyond mere availability.

- *SME engagement and urgency is low.* Multiple respondents, including industry association representatives, note that SMEs are not yet motivated to engage. Reasons cited include economic pressures, the fact that no regulation is yet in force, and a general tendency to "wait until the last minute." This is a readiness problem, not purely an information problem.
- *Confusion about regulation timing and implementation.* Several respondents specifically call out confusion around *when* requirements will apply and *how* they will affect businesses practically. One respondent running webinars for SMEs notes that even after extensive outreach, "SMEs are still very confused about timing."
- *Lack of a single, authoritative, reliable source.* A recurring expression is the absence of one trusted, consolidated reference. One respondent put it plainly: they cannot point industry colleagues to "one reliable & compact source of information." The lack of final regulatory decisions is also blamed for creating an "information room" full of noise and incomplete guidance.
- *Misinformation and low-quality content online.* Two respondents explicitly mention misinformation or poor-quality information circulating online, meaning that simply finding information is not useful. In fact, SMEs may risk acting on inaccurate guidance.
- *Technology and AI seen as part of the solution.* A few responses suggest AI-driven tools or digital platforms as a way forward, indicating that the respondent community is already thinking about scalable solutions to the information problem.
- *Disproportionate compliance burden on small businesses.* Several respondents note that the cost, in time, money, and personnel, of navigating compliance falls disproportionately on SMEs compared to larger companies, which have dedicated compliance teams.

While the sample size of 27 respondents is not sufficient to draw statistically significant conclusions, weather across response categories or by organisational type, a close examination of text answers revealed several pattern worth noting. Among the “Yes” respondents (n=3), two of the three pointed to the existence of information including EC publications and draft standards, without mentioning of SME capacity, complexity, or structural barriers. One of the “Not sure” respondents (n=5) offered the observation that regulation information may exist for EU-based SMEs but is insufficient for non-EU companies trying to export to the EU.

Analysis across organisation types identified several interesting insights.

- *Large Organisations - Manufacturers* (n=4): All answered "No". One notes that customers come to them for guidance, with SMEs bearing disproportionate compliance costs. Another highlights that market maturity, including technical expertise, is not there yet. A third points to regulatory interconnectivity across business functions as the core complexity.
- *Associations* (n=3): All answered "No," and their explanations are grounded in direct experience of trying to reach SMEs. One describes running a dedicated website and webinar series since 2024, yet concludes SMEs are not engaging due to economic pressures. Another association describes the DPP approach as too complex and bureaucratic. A third states that actual regulations are "only understandable to experts".
- *SME - Manufacturer* (n=1): answered "Yes" and offered the most optimistic explanation, citing implementable EU standards already available as drafts. This is the only response that frames existing draft standards as sufficient.

3.1.2 REGULATORY INFORMATION QUALITY

More than half of the respondents, sixteen (59%), did not think the available regulatory information is of sufficient quality (Figure 5).

Eight (30%) answered “Yes” and three (11%) answered “Not sure” to “Do you think in general the quality of the available information in the public sphere is high, meaning the information is sufficiently accurate for informing high-level business decisions relating to DPP”. While the overall distribution points in the same direction as the previous question, that current information provision is inadequate, the response is somewhat more divided.

Breaking down responses by organisational type (**Figure 6**), both SME consultants, both standardization body respondents, the large organisation consultant, and the SaaS platform respondent all answered "No." Associations were predominantly negative, with two of three responding "No" and one "Yes." DPPSPs again mirrored the overall trend, with six answering "No," three "Yes," and two "Not sure." Notably, large organisation manufacturers showed a more mixed picture, two answered "Yes," one "No," and one "Not sure". The SME manufacturer and the university respondent each answered "Yes," consistent with their responses on the previous question.

FIGURE 5: SUFFICIENT QUALITY OF REGULATORY INFORMATION

FIGURE 6: SUFFICIENT QUALITY OF REGULATORY INFORMATION BY ORGANISATIONS

To complement the quantitative responses, respondents were invited to elaborate on **their assessment of information quality**. As with the previous question, a word cloud analysis was conducted on these responses and is presented in **Figure 7**. Text analysis was conducted and a few key themes have emerged and are described below. Note that even the "Yes" responses are heavily qualified, shedding more lights into the statistics described above.

- Regulatory incompleteness is the root cause of poor quality.* This is the single most distinctive theme that barely surfaced in the previous explanation analysis. That is information quality is poor not because of poor communication, but because the regulation itself is unfinished. Multiple respondents make this explicit:

 - "Still a lot of unknowns with delegated acts linked to DPP"
 - "Missing legislation. Developing DPP guessing likely boundary conditions."
 - "We don't know the 16 data points yet, so the information is not fully accurate or relevant"
 - "The missing DPP legislation makes decisions very hard"
 - "Much of the detail is missing, not decided yet upon by the legislator"

- "I do mention CIRPASS-2 website, but not all have time to spend hours reading the papers"
 - Large manufacturers credit CIRPASS documentation with helping them build a regulatory roadmap
 - Note that even those who praise CIRPASS-2 immediately qualify it: reach is uncertain, content is too lengthy for time-poor practitioners. So, the best available resource is still falling short of what SMEs actually need.
- A *distinctive point* raised by a respondent stands out: government enterprise bodies are failing to educate businesses, partly because they themselves have not been educated. This cascading knowledge gap, from regulator to intermediary to SME, is a structural problem that goes beyond content quality.
 - The "Yes" responses are telling because they are almost uniformly self-contradicting. Every single "Yes" respondent adds a "but":
 - "Yes, but not easy to find and a lot of wrong communication is available online"
 - "Yes, but there is a lot of misinformation, not seldom published with commercial interest"
 - "Yes, but the in-house expertise might not be there"
 - "Yes, but difficult to retrieve for those not already in the DPP dialogue"
 - "Yes, but some of it is contradictory or could be misinterpreted, there needs to be a trusted source of truth"

3.1.3 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SMEs

Respondents were also asked to provide **recommendations for improving the availability of knowledge to SMEs on evolving product regulations and DPP implementation**. In contrast to the preceding open-text questions, which were primarily diagnostic in nature, the responses here are notably action-oriented, with respondents offering concrete suggestions that in many cases reflect their own professional context and experience. A word cloud of these responses is presented in **Figure 8**. The most prominent terms point to a clear consensus around a handful of recurring solution clusters, including centralized information resources, targeted guidance, and structured training or capacity-building initiatives. Alongside these dominant themes, a number of more distinctive recommendations also emerge, reflecting the diversity of organisational perspectives represented in the sample.

- **Recommendation Cluster 1:** A single, centralized hub of information. The most frequently recommended solution across different organisation types is the creation of a one-stop-shop for DPP and ESPR information. This appears in multiple forms:
 - "Information to be centralised and provided in a simple, structured and up-to-date way, via a single website, short webinars, Q&A helpdesk"
 - "Information could be made accessible in a one-stop-shop format without having to go through various links"
 - "Maybe one website with both general/high-level information and more detailed documentation"
 - "To centralise more documents/links/whitepapers by categories as CIRPASS-2 have been doing"
 - "A specific cluster for simplifying information access"

- "The Compliance Navigator and a filterable legislation database with an AI upgrade for natural language questions"
- An alert system for CIRPASS-2 stakeholders when new documents are published
- "A social media-style feed of CIRPASS information, not newsletters, something more consistent"
- *Recommendation Cluster 5: Positive framing and broader public outreach.* One recommendation stands out as genuinely distinctive, which is that the *tone of communication needs to change*, not just the format or channel. The respondent suggests TV spots, social media ads from trusted associations, and marketing that highlights the *positive aspects of DPP* rather than creating fear. This is the only response to address the motivational dimension of SME engagement, which connects directly to the previous observation that SMEs are disengaged partly because the topic feels threatening and burdensome.
- *Recommendation Cluster 6: Regulatory simplification at the source.* Two respondents go beyond communication recommendations to state that the regulation itself needs to be simplified before any communication strategy can work:
 - "Keep the ESPR and DPP requirements simple in a first step, make them work, scale later"
 - "DPP policies for SMEs should aim to avoid regrettable negative impacts, as was proven the case with ESG reporting regulations"
 - This is a more radical recommendation than the others. It implies that no amount of better communication will solve the problem if the underlying regulatory architecture remains inaccessible to SMEs. The ESG/CSRD references suggest respondents are drawing lessons from past regulatory rollouts.
- *Recommendation Cluster 7: Financial support for implementation.* One respondent proposes something entirely different from all others: *EU funding for SMEs* to pilot DPP implementation, specifically targeting the first year of adoption. This shifts the conversation from information access to economic enablement, recognizing that SMEs may understand what is required but lack the resources to act on it.

Without making broad generalization, dissecting these recommendations by organisation types appear to reflect the professional lens of each group.

- *DPPSPs* tend to recommend practical tools and channels, such as AI systems, toolkits, social media feeds, association partnerships.
- *Large manufacturers* focus on policy design and institutional responsibility to avoid CSRD-style failure, creating chatbots trained on SME-specific regulatory knowledge, and calling for clearer legislative guidance before the ecosystem can function properly.
- *Associations* recommend regulatory simplification and tailored solutions, reflecting their frontline experience of trying to reach SMEs who are overwhelmed.
- *Universities* are the most technically forward-looking, actively building compliance navigators, legislation databases, and AI-enhanced tools, and recommending these as models.
- *SME consultants* converge on centralization and structured access, a single website, categorized documents, Q&A helpdesks, likely reflecting their daily experience of searching for information on behalf of clients.

3.2 RECOMMENDATIONS OF DIGITALISATION POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Respondents were also asked to **propose digital transformation support instruments that could help SMEs become DPP-ready**. The question specifically highlighted the challenge of structuring product information, a pain point that has emerged consistently across stakeholder interviews, multi-stakeholder discussions, and industry consultations well beyond this survey, and which is widely regarded as one of the most practical barriers to DPP implementation across sectors. A word cloud of responses is presented in **Figure 9**.

The responses to this question are notably the most technically grounded in the survey. The respondents shift toward proposing concrete digital instruments and infrastructure. The word cloud reflects this shift, with prominent terms pointing to data management, interoperability, and platform-based solutions. Across the responses, core data challenge is framed as an information and data quality problem, which requires better tools for data collection, structuring, and validation, as well as a more structural and systemic issue, requiring shared infrastructure, standardized data models, or ecosystem-level coordination. Main recommendation themes are described below.

FIGURE 9: RECOMMENDATIONS OF DIGITALISATION POLICY INSTRUMENTS

- *Data collection and structuring as the core challenge, not information access.* Several respondents express that the central challenge for DPP readiness is actually collecting, structuring, and managing product data at the operational level:
 - "The main challenge is not on exposing data, but on gathering it and making it compliant with the upcoming requirements that nobody knows"
 - "First step is data collation and data storage, before even feeding data into DPP, SMEs need to digitise their supply chain and bring them all in one platform"
 - "Standardisation of the schemas for data collection is the most important instrument"
 - "DPP platforms should structure and guide the data gathering for SMEs"
 - "Harmonised input framework freely available"
- *AI as a structuring and personalisation tool.* AI recommendations in this column are more specific and operationally grounded than in previous text responses. Respondents here envision AI not just as a communication tool but as an active participant in DPP implementation:
 - "Dedicated AI agents can help fill missing information gaps automatically or by asking the user. AI can help SMEs collect and assemble the right information like a mosaic"

- "AI-based data collection and structuring"
 - A respondent references their own compliance navigator with an upcoming AI upgrade for natural language queries
 - Another respondent uses the "mosaic" metaphor to reflect the fragmented, multi-source nature of the information problem and suggests AI as the tool to synthesise disparate pieces into a coherent picture for each SME's specific situation.
- *Self-assessment and readiness tools.* Two respondents independently recommend self-assessment instruments as a critical first step:
 - "A readiness assessment"
 - "A self-assessment tool where you can find out whether you are affected based on your own products"
 - "Logical checklists with incremental steps"
 - One respondent's suggestion is particularly practical: an interactive tool that helps SMEs first determine *whether* they are even affected by DPP requirements, based on their specific product categories. This addresses a fundamental gap, which is that many SMEs do not know if or when the regulation applies to them, making any deeper engagement premature.
- *ERP/PLM integration as the missing link.*
 - A distinctive and practically significant insight provided: "Simple to implement ERPs/PLMs are essential. Even mid-to-large firms still use Excel.". This points to the reality that DPP data management cannot happen in a vacuum. It has to integrate with the existing (often basic) business systems SMEs already use.
 - ERP providers are also specifically called out by another respondent as potential key partners: "Involve established IT providers (e.g. ERP providers) more closely in the transfer, as they are often the main point of contact for digitalisation in SMEs."
- *Standardisation and shared infrastructure.* Several respondents emphasise that digital tools will only work if they are built on *common standards and shared infrastructure*:
 - "Standardisation of the schemas for data collection is the most important instrument"
 - "A joined approach using GS1, BSI, and ISO established standards effectively"
 - "GS1 Europe can provide support instruments"
 - "In-factory training and greater industry coordination and standardisation"
 - PCDS (ISO 59040) is mentioned by a respondent as a simple, ready-to-use standard taking only 1-2 hours to complete
- *Data governance, ownership, and liability is a largely ignored risk.* One respondent raises a cluster of concerns that no other respondent addresses: data ownership, supply chain partner confidentiality, and liability if data is incorrect. Their recommendation, including guidance on SME-friendly data spaces and model contract terms, points to a legal and governance dimension of DPP readiness that had not been mentioned.

- *Calls to slow down or make DPP voluntary.* Two respondents push back on the pace and ambition of DPP implementation itself:
 - "Make DPPs voluntary first. The ambition of the European Product Act is too much too early"
 - "Clarity, e.g. quick provision of missing parts like registry definition, delegated acts for DPP service providers"
 - One respondent draws a comparison to the Union Database, another EU digital initiative criticised for delays and over-ambition, to argue that rushing DPP implementation risks the same fate.
- *Physical implementation challenges.* One DPPSP surfaces a problem entirely absent from other text responses: the physical challenge of placing product identifiers (IDs) on products, particularly in the textile sector. Even if an SME has structured its data correctly, attaching that data to a physical product via QR codes, RFID, or other carriers has real operational and cost implications. This is a genuinely unique observation that points to a dimension of DPP readiness beyond software and information.

3.3 SUPPORT FOR AN ACCREDITED SME TRAINING PROGRAMME

A majority of respondents, seventeen (63%), consider an accredited SME training programme incorporating the latest regulatory information to be a useful instrument (Figure 10)

FIGURE 10: SUPPORT FOR ACCREDITED TRAINING PROGRAMME

The two Sankey diagrams presented in **Figures 11** and **Figure 12** reveal a compelling insight when cross-referencing earlier responses with training programme support. **Figure 11** shows that of the 19 respondents who indicated that affordable resources are insufficient, 11 went on to support the training programme, yet a further five answered "Not sure" and two answered "No," suggesting that even among those who identified a clear gap in information availability, the training programme proposition did not automatically translate into unconditional support.

Figure 12 illustrates that of the 16 respondents who considered the quality of publicly available information to be inadequate, nine supported the training programme, while six remained unsure, indicating that dissatisfaction with information quality does not straightforwardly convert into endorsement of a structured training solution. Taken together, the two diagrams suggest a broadly positive but cautious reception of the effectiveness of an accredited training programme as a remedy.

FIGURE 11: FROM PERCEIVED INFORMATION AVAILABILITY GAP TO TRAINING SUPPORT

FIGURE 12: FROM PERCEIVED INFORMATION QUALITY GAP TO TRAINING SUPPORT

Respondents who provided an explanation for their answer offer a more nuanced picture than the headline figures alone suggest. The open-text responses reveal that support for an accredited SME training programme, while broadly positive, is rarely unqualified. The explanations suggest that the training programme concept enjoys the strongest overall support of any instrument proposed in the survey, but that its design and delivery would need to carefully address the practical constraints facing SMEs in order to fulfil its potential.

- *What supporters agree on:* The core case for a training programme is made consistently across multiple respondents: SMEs are actively looking for it, training is more effective than merely informing, and the cross-sectoral reach of DPP regulation means the need is broad.
- *However, even “Yes” answers come with conditions.*
 - Condition 1: Timing: is it too early?
 - This is the most significant insight. Several respondents express concern that a training programme launched now would be premature:
 - "Until DPP legislation is finalised, I don't believe a training programme would be helpful. Things are moving too quickly at this point"
 - "It may be too early? Any programme has to be tailored to affected sectors"

- "Many companies are still not interested due to lack of regulatory clarity on data points for the DPP"
- "DPP introduction for SMEs needs to be achievable in terms of CAPEX, OPEX and resources, current trends are not encouraging"
- This timing concern is directly connected to the regulatory incompleteness theme identified earlier. A training programme built on incomplete or shifting regulatory content risks becoming outdated quickly, potentially adding to rather than reducing confusion.
- Condition 2: Training alone is not enough
 - Multiple respondents who support a training programme immediately qualify that it must be part of a broader package of support:
 - "Yes, but not only, SMEs need instruments and money to invest in a greater industry digitalisation effort"
 - "Yes, plus a resource repository"
 - "Yes, it can definitely help to inform, but probably the biggest challenge is to access the DPP attributes in their supply chains"
 - One respondent states: SMEs don't just need training, they need "a tool enabling them to identify good solution providers"
 - This cluster of responses reinforces the insight indicating that information and training address awareness and understanding, but the harder problem is operational implementation, including data collection, supply chain digitization, and access to affordable technical solutions. Training is a necessary but insufficient condition for DPP readiness.
- Condition 3: Accreditation by whom, and does it matter?
 - A respondent raises the question: who would provide the accreditation, and is official accreditation even necessary? They express uncertainty about whether Commission-level accreditation is required or appropriate. This is a governance question with real implications such as accreditation by the European Commission would carry weight but may be slow and bureaucratic; accreditation by industry bodies or associations would be faster but potentially less trusted.
- Condition 4: Sector tailoring
 - Two respondents stress that training must be sector-specific rather than generic:
 - "Any programme has to be tailored to affected sectors"
 - "The training will be necessary since the regulations are affecting every side of the industry"
 - The DPP's phased rollout by product category (textiles, electronics, batteries, construction, etc.) means that the regulatory details vary significantly by sector. A one-size-fits-all training programme risks being either too generic to be actionable or too complex to be accessible.
- *The "No" responses:* Only two respondents explicitly answered "No,", reasoning that:
 - Standardisation bodies already inform in the proper way, making a separate accredited programme unnecessary
 - Companies are not yet interested due to lack of regulatory clarity, meaning demand for training is not there yet, not that training is inherently a bad idea

3.4 SUPPLEMENTARY QUALITATIVE EVIDENCE ON LEGISLATIVE COMPLEXITY AND DIGITALIZATION POLICY

To complement and deepen the findings from the main EWG1 survey, a very short follow-up survey was conducted in March 2026 with EWG1 respondents. Rather than a standalone survey, this was designed as a targeted qualitative probe, inviting practitioners to share concrete examples from their own experience of two specific issues that emerged as recurring themes in the main survey: the practical implications of legislative complexity and lack of harmonisation, and the perceived usefulness of existing EU and national digitalisation policies for DPP implementation.

Six responses were received, spanning sectors including textiles, construction, and electronics. While the sample is small, the respondents provided concrete examples, describing specific regulatory conflicts and challenges encountered in the course of preparing for DPP implementation. Below is a brief summarisation of key highlights:

- **Legislative complexity and lack of harmonisation:** a direct barrier to DPP implementation. Issues ranged from conflicting data format requirements across ESPR, Textile Labelling Regulation, and EPR, to the absence of the textile Delegated Act, which has left SMEs unable to invest with confidence. One respondent noted that even REACH Substances of Concern tracking, a pre-existing obligation, cannot be integrated into structured DPP datasets due to the lack of digital systems across multi-tier supply chains
 - *Regulatory fragmentation:* Overlapping obligations under ESPR, Textile Labelling Regulation, and EPR requiring identical data in incompatible formats, forcing duplicated reporting
 - *Disproportionate scope & cost:* Server infrastructure requirements exceeding core DPP needs; data space costs borne entirely by the submitting company; double-maintenance of paper and digital safety data.
 - *Standards / architecture paralysis:* too many initiatives to follow (e.g. DIN, GS1, UNTP, CEN/CENELEC, CIRPASS-2, JTC 24)
 - *Competitive intelligence risk:* Open DPPs could allow competitors to download business data “which would not be shared in a non-DPP world.”
 - *Non-EU exclusion risk:* Non-EU SME suppliers lack digital infrastructure and cannot self-declare data without Conformity Assessment, risking market exclusion
 - *Agentic commerce & competitiveness:* Chinese manufacturers already ahead on ISO 22057, 23387, 23386. EU companies awaiting clarity “will lose out in AI-supported sourcing tools used by buyers
- **Digitalisation policies: perceived usefulness and effectiveness.** ESPR itself was the only instrument credited as a genuine digitalization driver, forcing the shift from “Excel files, PDFs, test reports” to structured data, but still not sufficient due to the absence of finalized textile delegated acts. GS1 Digital Link and EPCIS are directionally useful but adoption remains “challenging for SMEs due to technical complexity and implementation costs.” National smart manufacturing programmes in textile-producing countries were described as helpful but “not designed specifically for DPP compliance,” requiring additional translation work. The Horizon EIC call was assessed plainly as “not working for SME”, 11-page proposals that are poorly explained. One respondent could name no relevant national policy at all, noting that trade associations are providing the most useful free support.

4 COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE (CoP) SURVEY

CIRPASS-2 CoP was surveyed during December 2025 – January 2026. The survey was motivated by a recurring observation from prior interviews and community engagements: DPPSPs occupy a uniquely influential position in the DPP ecosystem, often serving as the primary channel through which businesses first understand what a DPP is, what it requires, and what it can offer beyond compliance. These interactions have exposed a potential source of misalignment between the expectations that businesses bring to their early engagement with DPPSPs and the realities of what DPPSPs can currently deliver. The misalignment around creating timelines, costs, data readiness, and the scope of services can slow engagement, erode trust, and in some cases cause DPP implementation projects to stall before they begin. Addressing this gap could benefit from hearing directly from DPPSPs themselves.

This survey therefore aims to gather insights from the DPPSP community on how DPPSPs and their potential customers or clients can work effectively together. Responses from the DPPSPs' perspective are uniquely valuable due to their broad view of the DPPaaS industry landscape and their practical experience supporting a wide range of customers across sectors and geographies. The insights will help future customers and clients prepare themselves to collaborate with DPPSPs in an informed manner, and better understand the role of DPPSPs and how to evaluate them. This understanding is particularly relevant for SMEs, which are expected to rely heavily on DPPSPs to navigate DPP adoption given their limited internal capacity.

All responses have been treated as completely anonymous, and the survey was designed not to elicit any confidential, proprietary, or intellectual-property-related information, nor details of technical or solution designs. Neither the questions nor the analysis is intended to assess DPPSP regulatory compliance, evaluate performance, or imply that certain solutions are preferable to others.

The survey received 52 responses in total, of which 50 were retained for analysis following data cleaning to remove incomplete or unusable entries. Respondents were invited to **describe their sector focus** in their own words rather than selecting from a predefined list of categories. This open-ended approach was a deliberate methodological choice: it yields richer, more nuanced data, accommodates respondents serving multiple sectors simultaneously, and surfaces emerging trends that fixed categories would obscure, such as the prioritization of certain regulated sectors like batteries and textiles, or the growing number of providers explicitly positioning themselves as sector-agnostic or SME-focused rather than industry-specific.

There are a few key observations from the sector groupings:

- Textiles dominate overwhelmingly, reflecting the sector's early DPP regulatory exposure under ESPR. Nearly every respondent touches textiles, even when listing multiple sectors.
- Batteries are the second most common, and notably many respondents list batteries and textiles together, suggesting a cluster of providers intentionally building cross-sector capability around the two.
- Multi-sector coverage is the norm, not the exception. Very few respondents name a single sector exclusively; most list two to four, signalling that DPPSPs are deliberately hedging against regulatory uncertainty by broadening their scope.
- The "sector-agnostic" cluster is significant. Several providers have made a strategic choice to define themselves by customer size (SMEs) or service type (PIM, compliance consulting, logistics) rather than by product sector, which is a distinct market positioning emerging in the ecosystem.
- Construction and furniture appear more often than might be expected, hinting at growing awareness of upcoming ESPR obligations in those categories

4.1 DPPSPs ACTING AS DPP KNOWLEDGE PROVIDERS

FIGURE 13: FREQUENCY OF HAVING TO EDUCATE CLIENTS ON DPP

The majority of service providers find themselves having to provide basic DPP knowledge to prospect customers very often, 33 (66%) or often, 12 (24%) (Figure 13).

In other words, 9 in 10 DPPSPs are regularly educating their clients on DPP fundamentals before substantive engagement can begin. This near-unanimous finding underscores the core challenge motivating this survey: the educational burden on DPPSPs is not an occasional inconvenience but a structural feature of the current market, one that consumes provider capacity and delays the progression from awareness to implementation.

Respondents were asked to describe, in their own words, what **support they wished they had to help educate their prospect customers on DPP**. This open-ended format was chosen to capture the full range of needs without constraining respondents to predefined options. The responses cluster into **5 main support needs**:

- *Reliable training materials*: by far the most requested, mentioned explicitly by nearly 60% of respondents. The word "reliable" appears 16 times, suggesting that the concern is not simply a lack of materials but a lack of trustworthy ones.
- *Clear timelines & regulatory roadmaps*: many ask for sector-specific timelines showing *when* DPP becomes mandatory, what delegated acts to expect, and what preparation is needed at each stage. The uncertainty around deadlines is clearly a friction point in client conversations
- *Industry associations & expert networks*: access to credible third-party validators to back up what providers are telling clients, lending authority to the education process.
- *Case studies & real-world examples*: especially sector-tailored ones, to move conversations beyond regulation into tangible business impact.
- *Simplified, structured frameworks*: clients seem overwhelmed; respondents want short overviews, checklists, "at-a-glance" summaries, and data field guides rather than dense regulatory text

A closer examination of the training and support needs, cross-referenced against the sectors that the respondents operate in, may reveal further nuances worth exploring. Some observations are described below.

- *Textile / Fashion*: Requests are broad and consistent: reliable training materials, clearer timelines, case studies, and authority-backed content.
- *Battery*: Respondents reference the Battery Pass as a model. Requests focus on timelines and compelling business arguments.
- *Construction / Furniture*: Emphasis on structured information and official EU validation.
- *Electronics / ICT*: Mostly echo the training materials theme, but one highlights multi-sector complexity: products crossing categories
- *PIM / Generalist / SME-focused*: The most detailed and nuanced responses.

4.2 GETTING READY TO WORK WITH DPPSPs

FIGURE 14: KEY PERSONNEL NEEDED IN EARLY DPP IMPLEMENTATION

For a DPPSP engagement to move forward effectively, the right cross-functional representation must be present from the outset.

Respondents were asked to identify which key personnel from a prospect customer's organisation should be involved in early-phase engagement with DPPSPs, selecting all roles that apply. The intention behind this question is practical and rooted in a frustration commonly experienced by DPPSPs: client organisations frequently send the wrong people to initial DPP meetings, resulting in conversations that cannot progress, content that must be repeated, and momentum that is lost.

More fundamentally, this question addresses the understanding that DPP is not simply an ESG reporting exercise or a sustainability initiative that can be handled by one team in isolation. It touches data infrastructure, supply chain operations, product design, legal compliance, and commercial strategy simultaneously.

The results (**Figure 14**) reflect this clearly. With 50 respondents selecting all applicable roles, *Sustainability/ESG* leads with 42 selections, unsurprisingly, given that DPP is most commonly first encountered through a sustainability lens. However, *Supply Chain*, *IT*, *Legal/Compliance*, and *Product Management* follow closely, reinforcing that DPP readiness is an organisational challenge, not a departmental one. *Sales & Marketing* also features prominently.

FIGURE 15: SHOULD COMPANIES TAKE ON SOME PREPARATION?

The majority of DPPSPs, 35 (71%), indicated some preparation by prospect customers is helpful before engaging a DPPSP (Figure 15)

This question was designed to address a fundamental expectation gap: should prospect customers arrive at the table having done some preparation, or can they reasonably rely on their DPPSP to guide them through everything from scratch? Managing this expectation upfront matters, customers who assume a fully managed, hands-off service may be frustrated by the demands placed on them during onboarding, while DPPSPs who expect clients to arrive data-ready may find early engagements slower and more resource-intensive than anticipated.

The result appears to suggest that the engagement with DPPSPs works significantly better when clients have done some groundwork first. This may not be a binary choice between full self-sufficiency and full reliance. It rather signals that the most productive DPPSP relationships are collaborative from the start, with customers bringing a baseline of internal awareness, data visibility, and organisational readiness that allows the DPPSP to focus on implementation rather than foundational education.

Respondents who indicated in the previous question that some customer preparation is beneficial were then asked **to rank eight possible preparation activities** from most to least useful. 44 responses received. A weighted scoring system was applied: for each respondent, the activity ranked first was assigned the highest points (equal to the total number of activities ranked, N), with each subsequent rank receiving one point fewer. The total aggregated score for each activity is the sum of these weighted points across all respondents, and the average score is derived. **The results reveal a clear hierarchy (Figure 16).**

- *Regulatory understanding*, specifically, understanding DPP requirements for specific products and what data is mandatory versus voluntary, ranked first, followed almost identically by *Internal ownership and decision-making rights*, reflecting the importance of knowing who within the organisation is empowered to make DPP-related decisions before any external engagement begins. These two activities sit in a tier of their own, scoring notably higher than the rest.
- *Data availability assessment*, a high-level mapping of product and supply chain data, ranked third, followed by *Budget and cost expectations* and *Organisational readiness to work with a DPPSP*.
- The bottom three activities scored lower, though this likely reflects their perception as secondary steps rather than they are unimportant.

FIGURE 16: PREPARATION ACTIVITY PRIORITY BASED ON USEFULNESS

Respondents were offered the opportunity to supplement the ranked list from the previous question with any **preparation activities** they felt were missing or insufficiently captured by the predefined options. As an open-ended follow-up, it serves to reveal what the community believes is still absent from that picture. Responses cluster into **four preparation pillars**:

- Internal alignment & ownership:** The most recurring theme. Respondents emphasize that DPP is not an IT or compliance project, it is cross-functional. Specific recommendations include securing C-level buy-in, identifying internal champions across departments (not just one team), establishing a dedicated DPP project team, and clarifying internal decision-making authority. One states: *internal silos and internal competition need to be surfaced openly before engagement can work.*
- Data readiness:** Prospects need to understand what data they hold, where it lives, and what's missing before any DPPSP engagement begins. Activities recommended include data audits, ERP system readiness assessment, and starting to collect product-specific data in standardized ways. Several note that data fragmentation is the silent blocker: customers often don't know what they don't know.
- Regulatory & market education:** Prospects should read about DPP regulations proactively, assess their risk exposure (market access, fines), understand which regulations apply to their sector, and identify relevant use cases. One respondent recommends a competitive/market analysis as a starting point.
- Supply chain visibility:** Customers need to map their supply chain before a DPPSP can help them effectively. This includes knowing what's in their products, where materials come from, and having early supplier engagement for transparency documentation.
- Note that one respondent pushes back on the framing entirely, arguing that *"more responsibility for the success of a DPP project has to be carried by the DPPSP"*, not the customer. This is a minority view but worth noting as a service design consideration.

Respondents were also asked to **recommend specific tools or frameworks to prospect customers getting ready to work with a DPPSP**. Where the previous questions focused on *what* businesses should do to prepare, this question asks *with what*, seeking to surface a practical toolkit. The answers are notably sparse and uncertain, which is a significant finding in itself. Most respondents say "no," "don't know," or leave it blank. Below are some tools mentioned which include some private solutions.

- GS1 standards for unique IDs and data carriers
- Textile Genesis: sector-specific (textile traceability)
- PEF (Product Environmental Footprint) calculation as a light starting point for supply chain engagement
- Fashion Big Data (FBD) platform from an EU H2020 project
- getprodpass.com: a free sandbox for creating and learning about passports
- AWARE: mentioned positively for data collection during sourcing
- PIM platforms: one respondent makes a detailed case for Product Information Management as the foundational layer for DPP readiness
- A DPP readiness self-evaluation tool: mentioned as something that should exist (not necessarily that it does)
- An open-source tool being developed in Taiwan at the government level
- Traceability data platforms mentioned generically.

Respondents were invited **to specify additional considerations for micro-firms and SMEs in getting ready to work with DPPSPs**. This open-ended question therefore creates space for DPPSPs who interact with SMEs regularly and understand their constraints firsthand to share considerations, adaptations, and advice that go beyond the general guidance captured in earlier question. **Strong consensus on a core problem: SMEs face the same regulatory burden as large companies but with a fraction of the resources.** Several themes emerge from the text answers:

- *Financial burden*
 - Multiple respondents flag cost as the primary barrier
 - Requests for subsidies, EU funding, and government support appear repeatedly
 - One respondent explicitly calls for "free or inexpensive options from EU or service providers, otherwise this will be too burdening"
 - Another advocates for a freemium model to onboard SMEs before expecting payment
- *Simplicity & Usability:*
 - SMEs need lightweight, modular, minimum-compliance-first solutions
 - Recommendations include "WordPress-like" guided workflows, predefined templates, pre-configured attribute sets

- One respondent notes that SMEs are "very likely working out of spreadsheets" and need a simple upload/summarize tool as an entry point
- *Skills & capacity gaps:*
 - SMEs often lack IT, legal, and data management personnel
 - Training in digitisation skills is flagged as needed
 - Local industry associations are suggested as a delivery channel for training
- *Strategic reframe for SMEs:*
 - One respondent argues DPP may actually be *more important* for SMEs than large companies (competitive differentiation angle)
 - Another highlights that SMEs can't afford "expensive and heavy investment in new systems", data fragmentation needs to be solved with lightweight approaches
- *Data security concern* (unique outlier): One respondent raises a pointed concern about *trade secrets*, specifically, how micro-firms can protect proprietary information when DPP regulations may force disclosure to downstream customers. This is an underexplored issue that could become significant.

4.3 UNDERSTAND AND EVALUATE DPPSPS

Prioritize to ask DPPSPs about Regulatory compliance verification, Service scope, and Typical implementation journey (Figure 23)

DPPSP respondents were asked to shift their perspective to step into the shoes of a prospect customer and consider how they would go about understanding the role of a DPPSP and evaluating one before committing to work with them. Respondents were presented with a list of ten questions that a customer might reasonably ask a DPPSP during early engagement, and were prompted to rank them from most to least relevant. This exercise is particularly valuable because it draws on DPPSPs' accumulated experience of what customers actually need to know and what they often fail to ask, distilling that experience into a practical evaluation guide for future customers. Answered by 47 respondents, the same weighted scoring methodology used previously was applied here. The results present **a clear and instructive hierarchy**.

- *Regulatory compliance verification*, asking whether the DPPSP's solution complies with regulation and how that can be verified, ranked first, followed by *Understanding the scope of DPP services offered* ranked a close second, signaling that customers need a clear picture of what is and is not included before any meaningful evaluation can take place. *Understanding a typical implementation journey* came third, pointing to a practical appetite for knowing what the experience of working with a DPPSP actually looks like from start to finish.
- The middle tier, comprising questions about *The types of companies a DPPSP typically works with*, *What data customers need to provide and who is responsible for its accuracy*, and *What internal capabilities are expected at onboarding*, reflects concerns that are highly relevant but perhaps seen as secondary to establishing regulatory credibility and service scope first. Questions about *System integration and data storage*, and *Pricing structure* ranked lower, which is notable given that cost and data sovereignty featured prominently as concerns elsewhere in the survey.

- The lowest-ranked question, *Sharing anonymised use cases or lessons learned from previous deployments*, scored strikingly lower than all others. This is a thought-provoking finding given that case studies and real-world examples were among the most requested support materials.

FIGURE 17: SUGGESTED QUESTIONS TO ASK DPPSPs FOR EVALUATION AND SELECTION

Respondents were also provided with an open-ended question as an opportunity to go beyond the predefined list of recommended questions, to surface any **additional topics or considerations they believe prospect customers should raise when evaluating a DPPSP**. This helped to capture concerns, blind spots, and emerging issues that did not fit neatly into the provided options. The responses are particularly telling because they reflect what DPPSPs, drawing on their own experience, feel customers consistently overlook or fail to ask, making them an important practical resource for any business embarking on a DPPSP evaluation for the first time. **Five dominant themes emerge**, combining with the questions listed above to form a de facto DPPSP evaluation checklist:

- Data ownership, portability & vendor lock-in:** This is the most frequently raised concern, appearing in multiple forms. Prospects want to know: who owns the data? What happens if the relationship ends? Can data be exported in standardized formats? Can I migrate to a different provider without losing my product history? One respondent frames it bluntly: *"what if I decide not to continue my collaboration with you?"*.

- **Business stability & long-term viability of the DPPSP:** Several respondents flag that prospects are actively worried about choosing a provider that may not survive until DPP becomes mandatory. One puts it directly: *"a lot of companies currently fear this when looking for DPPSPs."* Questions around the provider's roadmap, commitment, and regulatory compliance longevity are essential due diligence items.
- **Technical depth & integration capability:** Respondents push prospects to go beyond surface-level demos and ask hard technical questions: Does the solution integrate with SAP S/4 or is it another silo? Does it use semantics or AI, or is it just a webapp? Does it automate GS1 Digital Link integration? Can it handle evolving delegated acts without expensive custom development? How are real-time data updates handled?
- **Security, liability & governance:** Who is liable if data is unavailable at the time of a regulatory request? Does the DPPSP have certified information security management? Is cybersecurity addressed? These questions point to an important legal grey zone, the boundary between platform responsibility and client compliance responsibility, that many providers have not clearly defined.
- **Scalability, flexibility & modularity:** Can you start with a pilot and scale incrementally? Can the solution handle multiple product categories? Can the customer self-manage DPP data without ongoing provider support? Are there multi-language capabilities? One German-language response asks these questions in detail, highlighting that incremental adoption without cost explosions is a key decision factor.
- **Notable outlier:** One respondent raises whether DPPSPs are appropriately licensing applicable patents, an unusual but legally valid concern.

Respondents were also prompted to **specify if micro-firms or SMEs have other considerations**. The themes are similar to previous responses, with more specification on what SMEs actually need from DPPSPs during the sales and onboarding process:

- **Cost consideration is existential, not an afterthought:** The cost theme appears in nearly every response. However, the text here adds nuance: it's not just about the DPP platform fee, it's about the *total cost of compliance*, including data collection effort, supplier engagement, and internal time. One respondent suggested to ask: *"how can I absorb the cost?"* Another notes SMEs should ask: *"What are the fees if we don't comply? Likelihood to get caught?"*.
- **Hands-on support & hand-holding is not optional:** Multiple respondents stress that SMEs without IT or legal staff need a fundamentally different service model, including more consulting, guided onboarding, and ongoing support. Phrases like "hand holding," "more consulting needed in general," and "guided solutions" appear repeatedly. A SaaS model with low configuration burden is strongly preferred.
- **Supply chain complexity for SMEs with non-EU suppliers:** One response highlights a potential problem. Small fashion brands working with suppliers in China, Vietnam, etc. face a double barrier: their own resource constraints *plus* suppliers who are not open to data sharing. This makes DPP compliance structurally harder for SMEs embedded in global supply chains.
- **Power imbalance in buyer-driven supply chains:** One of the most sophisticated observations in the entire dataset: SMEs risk having their DPP data *aggregated or overshadowed* by large companies, losing visibility and value capture. The respondent argues DPPSPs should adopt inclusive design, ensuring SME-level data visibility, fair representation, and mechanisms that let SMEs retain agency over their DPPs rather than being subsumed under corporate implementations. This is a systemic design issue that goes beyond pricing.
- **Regulatory scope confusion:** Respondents shared SMEs are still asking basic questions: *Do we need to comply? Which products are in scope? What exactly will be required?* This reinforces previous findings. If regulatory uncertainty is not resolved, it hits SMEs hardest because they can't afford compliance teams to monitor developments.

- *Regulatory rollback risk:* One respondent surfaces the idea: "Everyone I talk to is in a 'wait and see' mode as there is so much uncertainty on whether ESPR will follow the rollbacks seen for CSRD." This is a live market dynamic, meaning SME hesitancy may be rational given recent regulatory backtracking elsewhere in the EU sustainability agenda.

4.4 RECOMMENDATIONS FROM DPPSPs

The survey closed with a deliberately broad and open invitation, asking respondents to share **any additional recommendations they consider relevant** to fostering productive working relationships between DPPSPs and their customers, spanning policy, technology, process, and business model dimensions. This final question was designed to capture the kind of reflective, experience-informed insight that does not always surface in response to more targeted questions, giving respondents the space to step back from the specifics of customer preparation and DPPSP evaluation and offer their broader perspective on what the ecosystem, as a whole, needs to get right.

As practitioners who sit at the intersection of regulation, technology, and business adoption, DPPSPs are uniquely positioned to offer this kind of systemic view, and the responses to this column accordingly range from very concrete operational recommendations to higher-level observations about policy gaps, market maturity, and the structural conditions needed for DPP implementation to succeed at scale.

- *Role clarity between DPPSP and customer:* The single most common recommendation: clearly define who is responsible for what. DPPSPs should position themselves as technical infrastructure providers, not compliance consultants. One detailed response explains this distinction "*protects providers from liability for missing or inaccurate information while empowering clients to manage their own data governance.*"
- *Interoperability as a contractual mandate, not a nice-to-have:* Several respondents recommend mandating interoperability by contract, insisting on standardized data export formats, and establishing disaster recovery and data backup requirements. The EU Commission is also urged to provide a "*datapoints by sector*" template, a simple, authoritative reference that would reduce interpretation risk for everyone.
- *DPPSPs as intermediaries in policy dialogue:* A standout recommendation: involve DPPSPs directly in regulatory working groups and pilots, because they have a cross-company, cross-sector view that individual brands lack. One respondent states DPPSPs "*are able to look beyond individual company structures and design scalable, pragmatic solutions*", making them natural representatives of practical implementation reality.
- *Monetisation & value beyond compliance:* Multiple respondents urge the community to shift the conversation from "*DPP as cost*" to "*DPP as competitive advantage.*" Specific recommendations: develop ROI frameworks, explain how DPP data can be monetised, and showcase impact beyond minimum compliance. This is seen as the key to unlocking voluntary early adoption, especially among SMEs who need a business case, not just a regulatory mandate.
- *Urgency: start now:* One response expresses: "*Be quick. Start now!*". Several others echo the sentiment that the window for early-mover advantage is closing and preparation timelines are longer than most customers expect.
- *Regulatory timeline clarity as the #1 bottleneck:* "*The lack of product-specific requirements and timelines are the biggest bottleneck*", one respondent states this explicitly, and it echoes across the text responses to all questions. Until delegated acts are published with specific data requirements and enforcement dates, both DPPSPs and their customers are operating in productive ambiguity that limits commitment and investment.

5 CONCLUSION

This report presents preliminary findings from two surveys and a series of in-depth interviews conducted between December 2025 and March 2026 within the CIRPASS-2 stakeholder network. The analysis is descriptive in nature, documenting observed patterns and emerging themes rather than drawing generalised conclusions or formulating recommendations. Both will be developed at a later stage once additional evidence and stakeholder input have been collected.

Several recurring themes emerge across both surveys. The EWG1 survey reflects a broadly shared view that the current information landscape is inadequate. The problem is less about the existence of regulatory information and more about its consolidation, clarity, timeliness, and practical usability for organisations without dedicated regulatory expertise. Compounding this is a lack of urgency among SMEs, partly due to economic fatigue and partly because final rules are not yet in force. While the survey was framed around SME challenges, many concerns raised appear to apply to businesses more broadly. Regulatory fragmentation, inaccessible technical content, the absence of a single authoritative source covering aspects related to regulations and standards, and confusion around timing are challenges that cut across organisational types and sizes. Further work within CIRPASS-2 will seek to clarify the extent to which these difficulties are specifically more acute for SMEs or are shared more widely across the business community.

Importantly, DPP readiness is not primarily an information problem: it is a data infrastructure and digital transformation challenge that cannot be resolved through better communication alone. SMEs need not just to understand what DPP requires, but to have accessible, affordable, and interoperable tools that integrate with their existing systems and guide them through the data collection process step by step. This is a considerably more complex and costly challenge.

The CoP survey highlights the pivotal role that DPPSPs play in the ecosystem. Nine in ten service provider respondents report regularly having to educate prospective clients on DPP fundamentals before substantive engagement can begin. The survey also surfaces several clear takeaways regarding DPPSPs' own support needs. The most pressing unmet need is not more content, but trustworthy, verified content from EU bodies or recognised authorities. SMEs are identified as underserved, needing stripped-down, jargon-free resources that enterprise-focused materials do not provide. Localisation also emerges as an overlooked dimension, with responses pointing to gaps for non-English-speaking and non-EU-based stakeholders. The CoP survey findings on company preparation and DPPSP evaluation paint a consistent picture: the ecosystem is not yet ready to serve SMEs well. The tool landscape remains fragmented and lacks endorsement from trusted bodies, and the SME conversation repeatedly returns to two core needs: make it cheaper and make it simpler.

Across both surveys, the single most consistently cited systemic obstacle is the absence of finalised delegated acts and product-specific regulatory timelines. Regulatory timelines remain the hardest topic to address in client conversations, as uncertainty creates the most friction. This also constrains both businesses and DPPSPs in how much investment and commitment they can reasonably make at this stage.

Finally, it is worth noting that while respondents were asked specifically about policy recommendations, their responses span technical, business, and policy dimensions, reflecting the multi-stakeholder nature of the DPP challenge. A further layer of analysis is planned, going beyond the explicit statements captured here to examine broader patterns, tensions, and gaps in the data. These insights, combined with ongoing interviews and stakeholder consultations within CIRPASS-2, will form the basis for developing and validating concrete recommendations to support large-scale DPP implementation across sectors in a way that is practical and inclusive of businesses of all sizes and origins.